

Kinetics of Oxidation of some Substituted *N*, α -Diphenylnitrones by Bromamine-B in Acid Medium

M. UMA, M. GOPALAKRISHNAN, J. JAYABHARATHI and V. THANIKACHALAM

Department of Chemistry, Annamalai University, Annamalainagar-608 002

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Kinetics of oxidation of *N*, α -diphenylnitrones by sodium *N*-bromobenzenesulphonamide (BAB) in aqueous acetic acid containing perchloric acid have been studied. The main products are benzaldehyde and nitrosobenzene. While each oxidation is first order each in [oxidant] and [substrate], the rate is almost independent of [HClO₄]. Variation of ionic strength of the medium or addition of reduced product of the oxidant [BSA] has no or negligible effect on the rate of reaction. The solvent isotope effect has been studied by using heavy water. The reaction has been studied for some *meta*- and *para*-substituted *N*, α -diphenylnitrones at four temperatures, viz. 30, 35, 40 and 45° and thermodynamic parameters calculated. The validity of Hammett equation for the reaction is tested. A probable mechanism has been proposed.

Although *N*-bromamines have been employed as analytical reagents for the estimation of a variety of reductants there is meagre information about their kinetic behaviour in solution. Kinetics of oxidation of some substrates have already been reported¹. The kinetic studies on nitrones are rare. Only a few reports are available in the literature². But no information is available for the oxidation of nitrones by *N*-bromamines. Hence, it was thought interesting to investigate the oxidation behaviour of bromamine-B (BAB) towards aldonitrones and this is reported here.

Results and Discussion

Aldonitrones being in large excess, plots of log [BAB] vs time are linear, indicating a first-order dependence on [BAB]. The rate was unaffected on varying [BAB] (Table 1). The rate increases steadily with increase in [nitrone] and a plot of log k_{obs} vs log [nitrone] gave a straight line with unit slope ($r = 0.994$; slope = 1.08) showing a first order dependence of rate on [nitrone] (Table 1). Varying either [H⁺] or [NaClO₄] has no effect on the reaction rate (Table 2). Addition of [BSA], [Br⁻] and [Hg²⁺] did not alter the rate of oxidation (Table 3). The rate of the oxidation was unaffected by decreasing the dielectric constant of the medium. The rate of the reaction did not change when water was replaced by heavy-water (Table 4). The reaction was carried out at four different temperatures

(30, 35, 40 and 45°) and thermodynamic parameters are $\Delta S^\ddagger = -57.06 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta H^\ddagger = 62.40 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. An addition of acrylonitrile showed no influence on the rate of oxidation.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF REACTANTS ON REACTION MEDIA AT 35° IN ACID MEDIA

[HClO₄] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, DMF-H₂O : 60% (v/v)

10 ³ [BAB] mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ [NO] mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ k_{obs} s ⁻¹	k_2 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
0.50	1.00	2.084	-
0.75	1.00	2.364	-
1.00	1.00	1.949	-
1.50	1.00	1.505	-
2.00	1.00	1.698	-
1.00	0.25	0.377	0.151
1.00	0.50	0.994	0.199
1.00	0.75	1.345	0.179
1.00	1.00	1.949	0.195
1.00	1.25	2.501	0.200
1.00	1.50	3.015	0.201
1.00	1.75	3.422	0.196
1.00	2.00	3.444	0.172

Mechanism and rate law : Based on the above observation, the following mechanism may be proposed. The substrate which behaves as an iminium³ salt exists in two resonating forms,

TABLE 2-EFFECT OF VARYING [H⁺] AND [NaClO₄] ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION AT 35°

[NO] = 0.01 mol dm⁻³, [BAB] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, DMF-H₂O : 60% (v/v)

10 ³ [H ⁺] mol dm ⁻³	10 ² [NaClO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ k _{obs} s ⁻¹
0.25	-	1.794
0.50	-	1.883
0.75	-	1.937
1.00	-	1.949
1.25	-	2.016
1.50	-	2.070
2.00	-	1.896
2.50	-	1.825
1.00	1.00	1.882
1.00	1.50	1.913
1.00	2.00	1.895
1.00	2.50	1.873
1.00	3.00	1.929

TABLE 3-EFFECT OF VARYING [BSA], [Br] AND [Hg²⁺] ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION AT 35°

[NO] = 0.01 mol dm⁻³, [BAB] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, DMF-H₂O : 60% (v/v)

10 ³ [HClO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ [BSA] mol dm ⁻³	10 ² [Br] mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ [Hg ²⁺] mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ k _{obs} s ⁻¹
10.00	0.50	-	-	1.917
10.00	1.00	-	-	1.971
10.00	1.50	-	-	2.028
10.00	2.00	-	-	2.136
10.00	2.50	-	-	2.158
10.00	3.00	-	-	2.022
2.50	-	1.00	-	1.908
2.50	-	1.50	-	1.900
2.50	-	2.50	-	1.981
2.50	-	3.00	-	1.912
10.00	-	1.00	-	1.990
10.00	-	1.50	-	1.989
10.00	-	2.00	-	1.990
10.00	-	2.50	-	1.952
10.00	-	-	1.00	1.912
10.00	-	-	1.50	1.940
10.00	-	-	2.00	1.902

TABLE 4-EFFECT OF VARYING PERCENTAGE OF SOLVENT ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION AT 35°

[NO] = 0.01 mol dm⁻³, [BAB] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³

% DMF	% H ₂ O	% D ₂ O	10 ³ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)
50	50	-	1.869
55	45	-	1.852
60	40	-	1.949
65	35	-	1.832
75	25	-	1.795
50	40	10	1.871
50	30	20	1.867
50	20	30	1.852
50	-	50	1.879

The attack of electrophile only takes place towards nitrogen atom rather than carbon atom. Bromamine-B (RNBrNa, where R = C₆H₅SO₂) is analogous⁴ to CAT and behaves like a strong electrolyte in aqueous solution, dissociating as⁵

The anion picks up a proton in acid solution to give the free acid, monobromamine-B, (RNHBr = N-bromobenzenesulphonamide),

$$K_a = 1.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ at } 25^\circ$$

The free acid has not been isolated, but in analogy with the chloro-compound, experimental evidence for its formation in acid solutions can be visualised. It undergoes disproportionation giving rise to benzene-sulphonamide (RNH₂) (I) and dibromamine-B (RNBr₂) (II).

$$K_d = 5.8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ at } 25^\circ$$

The species (II) and (I) hydrolyse to give hypobromous acid (HOBr),

$$K_h = 4.21 \times 10^{-3}$$

Finally, HOBr ionises as

The possible oxidising species in acidified BAB solutions are therefore, RNHBr, RNBr₂, HOBr, Br₂. If RNBr₂ were to be the reactive species, then the rate law predicts the second-order dependence of rate on [BAB], which is contrary to the experimental observation. Further, equation (6) indicates that the hydrolysis is slight and if HOBr is primarily involved, a first order retardation of rate by the added BSA is expected. However, no such effect was noticed. The solvent isotope effect also ruled out the involvement of HOBr in the reaction. Hardy and Johnston⁶ made detailed calculations on the concentration dependence of conjugate acid, HOBr and BrO⁻ ion on pH, in aqueous BAB (6×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) in pH range 7–13. It is seen from the results that [RNHBr] is high at pH 7 and is of the order of 4.1×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, while [HOBr] = 6.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ and [BrO⁻] = 1×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³. A comparison with concentration of species present in acidified CAT solution⁴, would indicate that RNHBr is the likely oxidising species in [H⁺] medium, for addition reaction product BSA have virtually no effect on the rate. That the rate of the reaction is independent on [H⁺], ruled out the involvement of RN⁻H₂Br in the slow-step. The Hg²⁺ ion effect also ruled out the formation of bromine molecule in this reaction. The absence of polymerisation by the addition of acrylonitrile in the course of the reaction showed that the reaction is free from radicals. Based on the above observation, the probable oxidising species would be RNHBr. The probable mechanism is given in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Rate law is

$$\frac{-d[\text{BAB}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{nitron}] [\text{oxidant}] \quad (12)$$

Effect of substituents : Effect of substituents on the rate of the oxidation has been studied with a number of *meta*- and *para*-(α -phenyl)substituted-*N*, α -diphenylnitrones. In general, the rate of the reaction is accelerated by electron-releasing substituents and retarded by electron-withdrawing ones. The relevant rate constants and the activation parameter are given in Table 5. Generally speaking, any substituent which increases the electron density at a reaction site would enhance the overall rate of the reaction. Due to electron-releasing hyperconjugative effect, *p*-methyl-, *p*-methoxy- and *p*-hydroxy-*N*, α -diphenylnitrones reacted faster than that of unsubstituted *N*, α -diphenylnitrones. Among these *p*-hydroxy-*N*, α -diphenylnitronone reacts faster of the series (Table 5). Such a high rate is due to direct mesomeric interaction of *para*-hydroxy group with the reaction centre.

The observed reactivity of chloro- and bromo-sub-

TABLE 5—TEMPERATURE EFFECT AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF BAB OXIDATION OF *N*, α -DIPHENYLNITRONS

R $\text{R} = \text{H};$ $\text{R}' =$	k_2 ($10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)				$\Delta H^\ddagger$	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	ρ	sd
	30°	35°	40°	45°	kJ mol^{-1}	$\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$		
H	11.1	19.5	25.5	39.0	62.4	57.1	0.991	0.085
<i>p</i> -Me	16.2	19.8	30.2	40.5	48.1	101.9	0.990	0.071
<i>p</i> -OMe	18.2	22.3	28.8	44.6	44.5	113.1	0.980	0.080
<i>p</i> -Cl	11.6	20.1	25.7	35.3	55.1	80.6	0.985	0.098
<i>p</i> -Br	10.3	16.2	23.7	30.2	55.1	81.8	0.992	0.071
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	6.7	10.9	15.4	25.4	66.9	46.7	0.997	0.049
<i>p</i> -F	12.3	17.2	23.0	36.0	53.6	85.7	0.994	0.069
<i>p</i> -OH	21.4	25.7	35.4	50.1	43.4	115.0	0.988	0.067
<i>m</i> -Cl	9.5	13.5	20.6	28.2	56.2	79.3	0.998	0.029
<i>m</i> -Br	10.0	14.4	22.4	30.6	58.4	71.5	0.998	0.040
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	7.9	11.2	18.2	25.1	60.5	66.7	0.997	0.051
<i>m</i> -F	10.5	14.6	19.3	31.6	54.6	84.1	0.989	0.078

stituted nitrones are in accordance with their inductive and mesomeric effects. The influence of *para*-nitro- and *meta*-nitro-substituents on the reaction rate are as predicted by the Hammett σ value (Fig. 1).

An analysis of the data has been made in respect of the linear free energy relationship. Table 5 reveals

that the entropy of activation is not constant throughout the series. One of the conditions necessary for the applicability of the linear free-energy relationship is the constancy of entropy of activation⁷. However, in most reaction series, this is not so^{6,8}. More generally, if the Hammett equation is valid at one temperature, the condition for its validity at any temperature is a

Fig. 1. Hammett plot of $\log k_{2(30^\circ)} / \log k_{2(40^\circ)}$ vs σ for BAB.

linear relationship between enthalpies and entropies⁹ and this is called the isokinetic relationship (equation 13).

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H_o^\ddagger + \beta \Delta S^\ddagger \quad (13)$$

where $\Delta H_o^\ddagger$ is the enthalpy of activation when $\Delta S^\ddagger = 0$ and usually has no physical significance and β is the isokinetic temperature. A plot of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ against $\Delta S^\ddagger$ gave a straight-line with an excellent correlation coefficient ($r = 0.998$). The isokinetic temperature obtained from the slope is 337 K. This linear correlation between $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ indicates that all the substituted *N, \alpha*-diphenylnitrones follow a common mechanism. However, Exner^{10,11} criticised the validity of such a linear correlation between $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ as these quantities depend on each other. When measurements at two different temperatures have been made, the experimental data can be treated by the equation¹¹,

$$\log k_2(T_2) = a + b \log k_2(T_1) \quad (14)$$

where $k_2(T_2)$ and $k_2(T_1)$ are the rate constants at temperatures T_1 and T_2 ($T_2 > T_1$) respectively. Applying equation (14), a satisfactory correlation ($r = 0.940$) is obtained when $\log k_{2(40^\circ)}$ is plotted against $\log k_{2(30^\circ)}$. This serves as an argument that the reactions of all substituted *N, \alpha*-diphenylnitrones follow a common mechanism.

The $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ values have been plotted against usual Hammett values giving a good correlations at all four temperatures (Table 5). The negative ρ value (Table 6) indicates that the transition state is more positively charged than the reactants. The small ρ value is attributed to the reaction centre away from the substituents.

TABLE 6—REACTION CONSTANTS FOR THE OXIDATION OF *N, \alpha*-DIPHENYLNITRONES BY BAB

Temp K	ρ	r	sd
308	-0.307	0.956	0.035
313	-0.283	0.952	0.032
318	-0.255	0.974	0.022

Experimental

Bromamine-B was prepared by the reported method¹². *N, \alpha*-Aldonitrones were prepared by the standard method¹³. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade (E. Merck). First order rate constants were determined under pseudo-first order kinetic conditions. The reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted BAB iodometrically.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : A number of reaction mixtures containing excess of BAB in the presence of perchloric acid, were kept for a day. The estimation of unreacted BAB indicated that one mole of BAB was used up for one mole of nitrone.

The reaction mixtures containing excess BAB were kept aside at kinetic temperature for two days. Then it was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was washed with 1% NaOH to remove benzenesulphonamide and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The products were analysed by co-tlc and ir spectrum. It showed that benzaldehyde and nitrosobenzene were the products formed in the reaction.

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